

This paper is the second of three papers I on Paul’s monumental words that we know as Romans 9. For my Ph.D. in Biblical Studies, I am required to create four independent research papers on a topic of my choosing. I have chosen to interact with Piper’s book, *The Justification of God* for three of the four. My first paper dealt with Piper’s treatment of Romans 9:1-5. This second paper deals with 9:6-13, and the third will focus on 9:14-23.

Unlike other Calvinist’s, Piper has approached this pivotal passage with a desire to interpret it within its historical context rather than impose theological systems upon it. He has also tried to avoid using it as a mine from which he can glean precious, predestinarian gems. I do not believe he has succeeded, but I honor him for his desire to approach Scripture on its terms. This paper focuses on my interpretation of Romans 9:6-13 and my engagement with Piper’s book.

Romans 9:6-13 and John Piper’s *The Justification of God*

In the Calvinist-Arminian debate supporters of both sides often put forward theological *systems*, sometimes designated by acronyms such as T-U-L-I-P for the Calvinist side and R-O-S-E-S for the Arminian.¹ Verses are placed within these systems to reinforce their various parts.² This is understandable and expected, but to my dismay, I have often discovered that little regard is given to the historical context in which the biblical authors wrote their words. In my short book on Romans 9, I addressed this problem.

Words, sentences, paragraphs, chapters, and the story – if we don’t know the story being told, the chances are, the deeper we drill from chapter to paragraph to sentence to word, the greater tendency we will have to isolate parts of Scripture and fit them into a different framework or a different story than the one being told by the writer, and we run the risk of badly missing the storyteller’s intent.³

One book from the Calvinist position cuts through this weakness and presents a thorough, verse-by-verse exegesis of a passage which is “Ground Zero” for many in the debate. It is John

¹ T-U-L-I-P for Total Depravity, Unconditional Election, Limited Atonement, Irresistible Grace, and Perseverance of the Saints and R-O-S-E-S for Radical Depravity, Overcoming Grace, Sovereign Election, Eternal Life, and Singular Redemption.

² Acts 13:48 and John 6:44-45, for example, are Calvinist favorites while John 12:32 and 1 Timothy 4:10 are Arminian favorites.

³ Williams, Jonathan, *Romans 9 and the Story Paul Was Telling*, WGS, San Antonio, TX 2013, 2.

Piper's, *The Justification of God: An Exegetical and Theological Study of Romans 9:1-23*. Piper admirably expounds from his Calvinistic perspective. He claims not to bring a theological system to the passage. Instead, he examines the passage verse-by-verse, paragraph-by-paragraph to display Calvinist coherence and to "...deal with Rom 9:1-23 *without* losing sight of its larger textual and historical context and *without* forcing it to answer dogmatic questions for which it was never intended."⁴

I highly respect John Piper as a man, a pastor, and a theologian, and I applaud his effort to avoid "cherry-picking" and embrace sound exegesis of this lengthy and pertinent passage. I also believe he has made several errors. I addressed four errors in his exegesis of 9:1-5 in my first academic presentation. In this presentation, I will address multiple errors in his analysis of 9:6-13.

First, I will examine 9:6-13 that the reader may become familiar with its emphasis. Then, I will engage with Piper's errors. My goal is to be clear and irenic so that no matter what persuasion one brings to the chapter, one may peaceably examine the evidence, come to theological conclusions, and be edified.

The Examination of Romans 9:6-13

It's all about Paul's statement in 9:6a, *God's word has not failed*. One can imagine an opponent saying, "Paul! Open your eyes. If Jesus is Messiah, as you claim, why are most of our people not following him? You say the elect people of God, and, therefore the recipients of the privileges you listed in 9:4 are cursed and cut off from these blessings. If this is so, either God

⁴ Piper, John, *The Justification of God: An Exegetical and Theological Study of Romans 9:1-23*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 1993, 15. Italics his.

has not been faithful to his promises or he does not possess the ability to bring the promises to fruition for obviously Israel has not been saved!”

Paul’s answer is Romans 9:6a. It is short, simple, yet powerful – *God’s word has not failed!* Despite the current unbelief of most of Israel, such unbelief in no way impugns God’s character or power. Anders Nygren puts it this way. “Two things are unshakably fixed for Paul: (1) that God gave His promises to Israel, and He never breaks them; and (2) that these promises of God have now been fulfilled in Christ.”⁵

Cranfield states, “This half-verse is the sign under which the whole of 9.6-29 stands – the sign and theme, indeed, of the whole of chapters 9 to 11.”⁶ The passage, therefore, is Paul’s opening move to defend the character and power of God; *the word of God has not failed*. Paul will explain why it has not failed, but before we examine his explanation, we must dig deeper into his opening statement.

Moo sees the “word” as “God’s OT word, with particular reference to his promises to Israel,” and even more specifically to the privileges just listed in verse 4.⁷ Black has a wider view. It refers to “...the whole plan and intention of God,”⁸ and Burge emphasizes the active nature of “word” by referring to it as “God’s effort.”⁹

Whether we define “word” narrowly or broadly, the point is the same. God’s word has not failed. “Paul tries to show that God’s word is not compromised by what has happened.

⁵ Nygren, Anders, *Commentary on Romans*, Fortress Press, Philadelphia, PA, 1972, 361.

⁶ Cranfield, C.E.B., *Romans: A Shorter Commentary*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1988, 227.

⁷ Moo, Douglas, *The Epistle of Paul to the Romans*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1996, 573.

⁸ Black, Matthew, *Romans*, Marshall, Morgan, and Scott, London, 1973, 130.

⁹ Burge, Gary, Cohick, Lynn H., Green, Gene L., *The New Testament in Antiquity*, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2009, 331.

Justification by faith, and with it the admission of Gentiles into the people of God without further condition, does not run counter to the promise ... of God nor to his trustworthiness.”¹⁰

The word “failed” is ἐκπέπτωκεν¹¹ which means to “...drop off, fall through, drift off course, or come up short in a financial sense.”¹² In rhetoric, it referred to someone who “...suddenly went silent and was at an utter loss; and stopping, he suffers a failure in his speech....”¹³ We cannot say which, if any, of these nuances were in Paul’s mind. They mostly help us gain insight into shades of meaning. We can say, with a fair amount of certainty, that Paul more likely had in mind the common idiom of the biblical and post-biblical tradition that God’s prophetic word would not fall.¹⁴

How does Paul deal with the glaring reality surrounding him that most Jews did not believe? Paul answers, *for not all who are descended from Israel are Israel*. Another way of saying this is that not all who descended from the ancient patriarchs are Israelites. If the majority do not believe, their unbelief only proves that they are not really Israel. Morris succinctly explains this. “Israel cannot be defined in terms of physical descent [I]t is created not by blood and soil, but by the promise of God....”¹⁵

¹⁰ Zeisler, John, *Paul’s Letter to the Romans*, Trinity Press International, Philadelphia, 1990, 240.

¹¹ *The Greek New Testament: SBL Edition*. Copyright © 2010 by Society of Biblical Literature and Logos Bible Software, <https://www.biblegateway.com>.

¹² Jewett, Robert, *Romans*, Fortress, Press, Minneapolis, MN, 2007, 573.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 573.

¹⁴ Byrne, Brendan, *Romans*, The Liturgical Press, Collegeville, Minnesota, 1996, 293. He points the reader to Joshua 21:45; 23:14; Ruth 3:8; 1 Samuel 3:19; 2 Kings 10:10; and Tobit 14:1.

¹⁵ Morris, Leon, *The Epistle to the Romans*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1988, 353. Here, Morris is quoting C.K. Barrett.

This was not Paul's first time to make such a statement in this letter. "Just as he redefines being a 'Jew' in 2:17-29, so here he redefines 'Israel' by appeal to Scripture, pointing to the pattern established by the word of promise...."¹⁶ Nor was this unique to Paul. Kasemann points out that the Qumran community believed itself to be the true Israel in contrast to the wider mass of Israelites,¹⁷ and Cranfield states, "... within the elect people itself there has been going on throughout its history a divine operation of distinguishing and separating, whereby the Israel within Israel has been differentiated from the rest of the chosen people."¹⁸

How does Paul establish this conviction that there is an "Israel within Israel"? Paul provides two illustrations from the history of his people, the Isaac/Ishmael story and the Jacob/Esau story.¹⁹ We turn first to Paul's words about Isaac and Ishmael.

⁷ nor are they all children because they are Abraham's descendants, but: "through Isaac your descendants will be named."⁸ That is, it is not the children of the flesh who are children of God, but the children of the promise are regarded as descendants.⁹ For this is the word of promise: "At this time I will come, and Sarah shall have a son."²⁰

"An Israel within Israel" has always been the case with the people of God. From the beginning with Abraham, not all descendants of Abraham were regarded as "children of promise." O'Neill says that Paul "... is wanting to find a way of showing a difference within the

¹⁶ Seifried, Mark A. "Romans," *Commentary on the New Testament Use of the Old Testament*, G.K. Beale and D.A. Carson, editors, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2007, 639.

¹⁷ Kasemann, Ernst, *Commentary on Romans*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI 1980, 263.

¹⁸ Cranfield, 228.

¹⁹ Moo points out that each illustration is based on two scriptures. For Isaac/Ishmael, he quotes from Genesis 21:12 and a blend of Genesis 18:10,14 and for Jacob/Esau he quotes from Genesis 25:23 and Malachi 1:2-3. Moo, Douglas, 1996, 571.

²⁰ New American Standard Bible Copyright © 1960, 1962, 1963, 1968, 1971, 1972, 1973, 1975, 1977, 1995 by The Lockman Foundation, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Romans+9&version=NASB>. All Scripture quoted will be the NASB unless otherwise noted.

physical descendants of Abraham and Isaac and Jacob ... that will explain why some Israelites have not greeted their Messiah when he came. The distinction hangs on their attitude to the promise....”²¹ Douglas Moo provides helpful insight.

The “calling” of descendants “in” Isaac therefore involves more than the promise of physical offspring for God promised that he would give many descendants to Ishmael as well as to Isaac (Gen. 17:20; 21:23). The advantage of Isaac lies rather in the spiritual realm: it is with Isaac, and not Ishmael, that God promises to establish his covenant (Gen. 17:21).²²

Black reinforces the emphasis of promise by pointing to the word order of verse 9.²³ Paul begins his sentence with the word, *promise: ἐπαγγελίας* γὰρ ὁ λόγος οὗτος²⁴. Murray captures this significance. “Isaac was born in pursuance of that promise.... In the case of Ishmael there were no such factors. He was begotten, conceived, and born in accordance with natural procreative powers. It is this radical difference in the birth of the respective sons that is summed up in the word ‘promise.’”²⁵

What was the promise God made to Abraham? Paul quotes two Old Testament passages. The first is Genesis 21:12, “In Isaac your descendants will be named,” and the second is a blend of Genesis 18:10,14, “At this time I will come, and Sarah shall have a son.”

Descendants is a translation of σπέρμα, “seed.” Byrne notes that “seed of Abraham,”

... occurs elsewhere in Paul (Rom 11:1; 2 Cor 11:22) and the wider Jewish and Christian tradition (cf. PSS. Sol 9:17;18:4; John 8:33, 37) as an honorific title for

²¹ O’Neill, J.C., *Paul’s Letter to the Romans*, Penguin Books, Baltimore, MD, 1975, 154.

²² Moo, 1996, 575.

²³ Black, 131-132.

²⁴ *The Greek New Testament: SBL Edition*. Copyright © 2010 by Society of Biblical Literature and Logos Bible Software, <https://www.biblegateway.com>.

²⁵ Murray, John, *The Epistle to the Romans*, Volume II, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1965, 11-12.

Israelites, with the specific connotation, in virtue of the promises to the patriarchs, of destiny to ‘inherit’ the blessings of salvation...²⁶

Paul makes this point – Ishmael was the seed of Abraham, but he was not the result of God’s promise. In addition, there was no need for “God to come” to make the conception of Ishmael possible. Abraham was still virile, and Hagar fertile. But that was not the case for Abraham and Sarah in their old age. Paul had already stated in his letter that Sarah’s womb was dead and Abraham’s body as good as dead (4:19). At this stage in their lives, it was necessary for God to empower their bodies. What an exhilarating night that must have been for Abraham and Sarah! But leaving such imagination aside, Paul uses their story to substantiate this point – *not all physical descendants of Abraham are children of promise*. Ishmael was a physical descendant, but he was not born by means of the patriarch’s faith in God’s rejuvenating power. In the same way, many physical descendants of Abraham lived in Paul’s day, but they were mere “children of flesh,” like Ishmael. They were not children of promise for they were not placing faith in the Messiah as Abraham placed faith in the promise of God. Another way to say this is, *they are not all Israel who say they are Israel*.

“But Paul,” we can hear an opponent say, “It is obvious that Ishmael was not a child of promise. His mother was an Egyptian servant. You must do better to prove your point!” Paul was ready and moved to his second illustration, the story of Jacob and Esau in Romans 9:10-13

¹⁰ And not only this, but there was Rebekah also, when she had conceived *twins* by one man, our father Isaac; ¹¹ for though *the twins* were not yet born and had not done anything good or bad, so that God’s purpose according to *His* choice would stand, not because of works but because of Him who calls, ¹² it was said to her, “THE OLDER WILL SERVE THE YOUNGER.” ¹³ Just as it is written, “JACOB I LOVED, BUT ESAU I HATED.

²⁶ Byrne, 293.

Isaac, the miracle son of promise from Abraham and Sarah, and his wife Rebekah conceived twins, Jacob and Esau. Both were legitimate, but only one advanced the purpose of God. Both could say they were “in Isaac” and “in Abraham,” true descendants of these men of faith. But Jacob, not Esau, was the recipient of the covenant.

Paul’s Greek emphasizes the equality between the two. He wrote, ἐξ ἑνὸς κοίτην, out of one “koiten.”

The Greek word koite literally means “bed” but has extended, euphemistic meanings in the sense of “marriage bed,” “sexual intercourse” and even “seminal emission.” Paul probably wants to underline the equality between the twins, Esau and Jacob, by stressing not simply that Rebecca had intercourse with one man ... but that they were conceived from one and the same sexual act.”²⁷

Thus, two legitimate sons of Isaac came from this one act of procreation, but the covenant that God first made with Abraham and affirmed with the son of promise, Isaac, he now establishes with Jacob. Paul reinforces this by quoting from Malachi 1:2-3, “Jacob I have loved, but Esau I hated.”

No Jewish person could argue with Paul on this point. Esau was just as much a full-blooded descendant of Abraham and Isaac as was Jacob. Yet, all would acknowledge that Esau and his Edomite descendants were not Israelites. Thus, Paul has underscored his point in 9:6b, *not all who are descended from Israel are Israel*. “Look around,” Paul says. “Yes, it is true that many who claim physical descent from Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob are not following Jesus as Messiah. But they are not Israel! Just as Ishmael son of Abraham and Esau son of Isaac are not Israelites, so today, we are surrounded by physical descendants who are not children of the promise, who are not children of the covenant. They are sons of flesh.”

²⁷ Byrne, 294. See also *A Greek English Lexicon of the New Testament*, Arndt & Gingrich, “κοίτη,” 440-441, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 1963.

This seems simple enough, and we could go merrily on our way to the next section of this great chapter, but three phrases in the text give us pause.

- before the twins were born and had done anything good or bad
- that God’s purpose in election might stand
- Jacob I loved, and Esau I hated.

Calvinist commentators seize upon these statements and herald them as evidence of God’s sovereignty in unconditional election to salvation. John Piper promotes this view.

... [J]ust as Isaac was a child of promise in that God willed in advance for him to be the heir of the covenant promises and then worked sovereignly (“I will come!” 9:9) to fulfill his will, so also God wills in advance for particular individuals within Israel to be his “children” and then by his Spirit sovereignly begets them anew. Thus the *principle* of unconditional election, evident in God’s choice of Isaac to be heir of the covenant is applied now to Paul’s contemporaries to explain how it can be that only “some” (Rom 11:14) Israelites are saved and yet the promissory word (9:6a) or purpose (9:11c) of God has not fallen. God’s promissory word has not fallen precisely because it is an “electing purpose” which does not depend at all on human “willing” or “running” and which therefore irresistibly accomplishes its goal by itself alone.²⁸

Piper interprets Paul’s opening statement *they are not all Israel who say they are Israel* with, “They are not all Israel because God has always elected only some to eternal salvation. God’s word has not failed because it has always been a sovereign word of unconditional election which we see in his selection of Isaac over Ishmael and Jacob over Esau. In the same way, today, God has elected only some to salvation. Those who follow Jesus as Messiah are unconditionally elected to salvation. Those who do not believe are not among the elect.”

Are Piper and the Calvinist position correct? I will address three issues to answer this question.

1. The coherence of 9:6-13 with 9:1-5
2. God’s purpose in election as stated in 9:11, and his love for Jacob and hatred for Esau as stated in 9:13
3. The sovereignty of God in saying, “I will come” as stated in 9:9.

²⁸ Piper, 70.

Engaging with Piper – The Coherence of 9:6-13 with 9:1-5

One of the great points of debate pertains to the purpose of election. Is it for salvation or historical task? One position has pointed to Paul's second biblical reference in the Jacob/Esau story, Malachi 1:2-3. There, the prophet is not talking about the individuals, Jacob and Esau. Rather, he is talking about their descendants, Israelites and Edomites. Thus, the argument goes, Paul's election in 9:6-13 is not about salvation but the historical task of nations.²⁹

Piper, fairly and honorably, acknowledges that many scholars hold to the "election to historical task" position.³⁰ But he disagrees with this interpretation for this reason; 9:1-5 expresses Paul's sorrow over unbelieving Jews who are cut off from Christ. They are under a curse. 9:6-13 is Paul's first step in explaining why they are lost and must, therefore, explain his sorrow over their lostness in 9:1-5. Thus, the election in 9:6-13 cannot refer to their historical task. It must refer to individual salvation/lostness. This is how Piper puts it.

It is a remarkable and telling phenomenon that those who find no individual predestination to eternal life in Rom 9:6-13 cannot successfully explain the thread of Paul's argument as it begins in Rom 9:1-5 and continues through the chapter.... One also looks in vain for an explanation of how the pressing problem of eternally condemned Israelites in Rom 9:3 is ameliorated by Rom 9:6-13 if these verses refer "not to salvation but to position and historical task."³¹

Piper is correct on one point; the two sections must match. But his Calvinist position fails for this reason. If, as he says, Paul is weeping over current Israel's lostness in 9:1-5, then the six

²⁹ Douglas Moo, a Calvinist, ably summarizes the debate: "The theological implications of this paragraph are hotly contested. Calvinists traditionally have found in these verses important support for the notion of unconditional election.... However, many interpreters are not so sure.... They note that Malachi 1:2-3, the text that Paul quotes in verse 13, use 'Jacob' and 'Esau' to refer, respectively, to the nations of Israel and Edom.... Romans 9:6-13 is not about the salvation of individuals at all, but rather, about the way God has sovereignly selected nations to carry out his plan in history." Moo, Douglas J., *Encountering the Book of Romans*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2002, 150.

³⁰ Piper, 57.

³¹ *Ibid.*, 58.

privileges of 9:4 must be salvation indicators and not just historical task privileges? If salvation, then, did they lose their salvation? But that would be unacceptable for a Calvinist. This presents a conundrum for Calvinists that I have not found addressed by Piper or any Calvinist because the blessings of election in 9:4 which he says belong³² to his kinsmen must refer to their historical task *which never included salvation*. Piper's issue loses its force, and the passage loses the coherence for which he seeks if 9:1-5 describes the loss of historical task and 9:6-13, according to his position, is about unconditional election to salvation! That is not coherence.

How do we know that the six privileges listed in 9:4 do not include salvation according to the Calvinist position? Piper explains it this way, "If Paul can show that God's ultimate 'purpose according to election' *never included the salvation of every individual Israelite*, then the situation described in Rom 9:1-5 would not so easily jeopardize God's reliability...."³³ Thus, the privileges of 9:1-5, do not include salvation, and 9:6-13 must *introduce* unconditional election as the reason why the blessings of 9:4 do not include salvation. F.F. Bruce reflects this theological move.

The present condition of Israel reproduces a pattern of divine action and human response which has been unfolded often enough in the past. Some have always opened their hearts to God's revelation, while others have hardened theirs; and by the variety of their response they have shown whether or not they were among those on whom God had set his sovereign choice.³⁴

Thus, in the mind of F.F. Bruce, John Piper, and other Calvinists, Paul must *begin* talking about unconditional election in 9:6ff with the stories of Isaac/Ishmael and Jacob/Esau to explain why the blessings of 9:4 do not include salvation. Yet, this leads to another problem that Piper

³² Paul uses a present active verb and two present active participles. His point is that these blessings are still theirs by right.

³³ Piper, 50. Italics mine.

³⁴ Bruce, F.F., *Romans*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1990, 177.

acknowledges. “We may grant for the sake of the argument, that in the demonstration of this principle of God’s freedom in election Paul uses *OT texts that do not relate explicitly to eternal salvation.*”³⁵ Piper admits that the Old Testament texts are about historical roles. But why would Paul use historical task texts if he is talking about unconditional election to salvation? Piper explains,

How else could Paul have argued from the OT for the principle of God’s freedom in election since the eternal salvation of the individual as Paul teaches it is *almost never the subject of discussion* in the OT? Therefore selection of texts may reflect *the limited scope* of his sources rather than a desire on his part to guard against the implication of predestination unto individual salvation.³⁶

Limited scope indeed! I would also change one word in Piper’s statement. When he says that election to eternal salvation of the individual is *almost never the subject of discussion in the OT*, I would delete the word, *almost*. It is *never* the subject of discussion in the Old Testament. Piper and other Calvinists have therefore made a theological move that Paul uses “election to historical task” passages as a paradigm to teach unconditional election. They must believe that Paul is *introducing* a doctrine not talked about in those texts. But this leads to another problem. Where, in Romans 9-11, or anywhere else for that matter, does Paul expound clearly upon sovereign unconditional election? One will look in vain for such a teaching. The closest passage is this one, Romans 9, but here, Paul uses “historical task” passages to prove his point. The Calvinist argument becomes circular. Nevertheless, Piper jumps from “election to historical task” to “unconditional election to salvation.”

We may grant for the sake of the argument, that in the demonstration of this principle of God’s freedom in election Paul uses OT texts that do not relate explicitly to eternal salvation. What cannot be granted without further

³⁵ Piper, 64. Italics mine.

³⁶ Ibid., 64. Italics mine.

argumentation is that Paul intends for this principle of God's predestining freedom to be limited to God's choice of persons or nations for historical roles.³⁷

Piper's argument is that we must not think that Paul used historical task passages *only for this purpose*. But again, where then does Paul expound upon unconditional election? If these passages are the launching pad, where is the flight path of the doctrine? It is nowhere.³⁸ Thus, we must reject the argument that 9:6-13 is about "election to salvation" if Paul uses "election to historical task" passages *and if he does not use them as a platform to expound upon individual election*.³⁹ We must also keep Paul's main point in mind. It is not to prove unconditional election. His main point is to prove that God's word, his covenant promises that he mentioned in 9:4 have not failed.

What about Paul's grief? We must remember that prophets and the Messiah wept over Israel for their historical judgments. One thinks of Jeremiah's tears,⁴⁰ Habakkuk's distress,⁴¹ and Jesus' weeping⁴² as the covenant curses came upon the people. Like them, Paul weeps for the judgments that will come upon the people and for their exclusion in participating in God's covenant purposes now going forward among the gentiles with a remnant of Israel.

³⁷ Ibid., 64.

³⁸ As we will see later, Paul concludes his argument in Romans 9 with verses 30-33 which speak of faith and unbelief, not election.

³⁹ I realize that some will point to the following verses in 9:14-23 as his exposition on unconditional election. But in a subsequent paper I will show why this is not so. In short, he continues using historical task passages.

⁴⁰ Jeremiah 9:1, "Oh that my head were waters and my eyes a fountain of tears, that I might weep day and night for the slain of the daughter of my people!"

⁴¹ Habakkuk 3:16: "I heard and my inward parts trembled, at the sound my lips quivered. Decay enters my bones, and in my place I tremble because I must wait quietly for the day of distress, for the people to arise who will invade us."

⁴² Luke 19:41-42: "When He approached Jerusalem, He saw the city and wept over it, saying, 'If you had known in this day, even you, the things which make for peace! But now they have been hidden from your eyes.'"

But the issue is not so easily settled. Paul does give clues that Israel has lost more than historical privilege and task. He did say his people were under a curse and separated from Christ. He will pray for their *salvation* (Romans 10:1). Piper latches on to this point. He speaks of “... the pressing problem of *eternally* condemned Israelites in Rom 9:3”⁴³ which explains the depths of Paul’s emotional duress. But I ask, “Were they, at that point in history, *eternally* condemned? Was there no chance of repentance?” It is my conviction that Paul did not view them with hopelessness. Otherwise, why would he pray for their salvation in 10:1 if he knows they have not been sovereignly elected to eternal salvation? Why would he speak of the possibility of the re-grafting of the ones cut off and the hardening lifted in 11:23ff? One could also ask why Paul is weeping over the non-elect status of some. We could use Paul’s own words against him. “Who are you, O man who answers back to God?”⁴⁴ Stop weeping and praying for them, Paul! They were never elect!

But Paul’s grief is genuine, and his hope is genuine. He weeps over *the possibility* of eternal judgment. They are in jeopardy, not because they are non-elect to salvation, but because they have not exercised faith, like Abraham, which is his initial concluding remark in 9:30-33. He prays and wishes for their salvation in chapter 10, and in chapter 11 he holds out hope that they will be saved if they do not remain in unbelief.

Elizabeth Johnson summarizes Paul’s first-century struggle and hope perfectly. “But not even those hardened are permanently excluded, since their fulness will further enrich the world

⁴³ Piper, 58. Italics mine.

⁴⁴ Romans 9:20.

(11:12), even as their being cast off has meant the reconciliation of the world, and their final reception will mean nothing less than life from the dead....”⁴⁵

Engaging with Piper – God’s Purpose in Election in 9:11 and His Love for Jacob and Hatred for Esau in 9:13

The second issue we must deal with is found in Romans 9:11-13.

¹¹ For though the twins were not yet born and had not done anything good or bad, so that God’s purpose according to His choice would stand, not because of works but because of Him who calls. ¹² it was said to her, “The older will serve the younger.” ¹³ Just as it is written, “Jacob I loved, but Esau I hated.”

First, Piper correctly connects the “would stand” of verse 11 with the “failed” of verse 6.⁴⁶ God’s word has not failed. Instead, God’s word stands. But what *word* is it that stands? Piper calls this “the key exegetical question forcing itself on us from the context, and it surfaces precisely in the interpretation of ἡ κατ’ ἐκλογὴν πρόθεσις....”⁴⁷

Piper believes it to be God’s sovereign word of unconditional election. “The phrase κατ’ ἐκλογὴν is in the attribute position in relation to πρόθεσις.... [I]t defines God’s purpose as an electing purpose, a purpose to be one who selects on the basis described in 9:11ab and 9:12ab, namely, freely, with *no constraint from or ground in human distinctives*.”⁴⁸

I find three problems with Piper’s interpretation. First, he emphasizes that God’s choice of Jacob over Esau before either did anything good or bad proves that God’s choice was made solely on the basis of his freedom to choose as he pleases and “with no constraint from or ground in human distinctives.” But upon closer inspection of the Genesis text, this is not true. When God

⁴⁵ Johnson, E. Elizabeth, *The Function of Apocalyptic and Wisdom Traditions in Romans 9-11*, The Society of Biblical Literature, Princeton Theological Seminary, Scholars Press, Atlanta, GA, 1989, 140.

⁴⁶ Piper, 49. “... Rom 9:11c says positively what 9:6a says negatively.”

⁴⁷ Ibid., 50.

⁴⁸ Ibid., 53. Italics mine.

spoke to Rebekah, he spoke of the characteristics of the children in her womb. God recognized that the two were the fountainheads of nations. God recognized that one nation would be stronger than the other. God recognized that the older would serve the younger. *God's revelation to Rebekah was all about distinctives!* Paul's point is that before Esau and Jacob lived, before they did anything good or bad to prove or disprove themselves, God chose one of them to move the covenant purpose forward. He chose Jacob, the younger and weaker of the two. It would not be Esau, the dominant one, the leader of men, the warrior, the skilled hunter. Instead, God's kingdom plan moved forward with the younger one, the one with the sedentary lifestyle, the one who raised sheep, and who had trouble keeping four wives and twelve sons in line! The way of the world would have been to choose Esau. He was a leader of men. He had the characteristics of an empire builder. But God had an important lesson to teach. His kingdom plan does not go forward based on ego, skill, or empire building. It goes forward by weak men who have the audacity to trust him.

The two stories provide two paradigms for Paul's situation. First, the Isaac/Ishmael story teaches that God's plan goes forward by faith in the promises, not human descent. This is the reason why Israel in Paul's time was failing. They were trusting in their lineage. Paul said it is trust in God's promises and power that counts. Second, the Jacob/Esau story teaches that God's plan goes forward with the lesser, the younger, the weaker.⁴⁹ This was and is crucial in a world that idolizes the strong. God's plan advances through the weak who call upon him, the greatest example being the crucified Messiah who was raised by the power of God.⁵⁰ Thus, Paul can say,

⁴⁹ Levine, Amy-Jill, *Short Stories by Jesus*, HarperCollins, NY, 2015. Levine shows how this is a pattern throughout biblical history and would be easily recognized by people familiar with the Old Testament, 50-51.

⁵⁰ 2 Corinthians 13:4 – "For indeed He was crucified because of weakness, yet He lives because of the power of God...."

God's word has not failed. It has always been established by faith in the promises and gone forward when the weak trusted God. Israel was going forward by natural descent and by their rigorous attempts at law-keeping. We can now contrast three paradigms:

Piper's Calvinistic Paradigm:

Paul used historical task passages to:

establish a principle that God is free to choose whom he wants to eternal salvation.

Non-Calvinistic Paradigm:

Paul used historical task passages to:

establish a principle that God advances his covenant purposes by faith in the promises.

establish a principle that God advances his covenant purposes through the weak who trust him rather than those who are skilled and mighty.

At this point, I ask, “Which of the paradigms resonates with the emphases of Scripture?”

When Paul or the writer of Hebrews speaks about Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob, what is the emphasis? Is it upon unconditional election or faith in God's promises?

Piper's second problem is that he makes the narrative of Scripture to be God's electing purpose free of all human constraints. He states,

[I]t defines God's purpose as an electing purpose, a purpose to be one who selects on the basis described in 9:11ab and 9:12ab, namely, freely, with no constraint from or ground in human distinctives. In short God's purpose is to be free from all human influences in the election he performs.”⁵¹

A few pages later he said, “God's purpose is to perform his act of election freely without being determined by any human distinctives....⁵² I find this to be shocking and tragic. Piper's Calvinism has caused him to lose the narrative of Scripture. For him, the narrative is that God is

⁵¹ Piper, 53.

⁵² Ibid., 56.

sovereign and can do anything he wants. He elects some to salvation and leaves others to damnation. But when one looks at the story of Genesis, one finds that God's purpose and the biblical narrative is the election of Abraham *for the sake of the nations* – “in you I will bless all the families of the earth,” (Genesis 12:3b).⁵³ The election of some is for the sake of the non-elect. Election is not the purpose. It is the means by which God's purpose to save all who will believe is accomplished. Isaac was chosen for the sake of the gospel one day going to the Ishmaelites. Jacob was chosen for the sake of the Edomites one day receiving the gospel. The story of Scripture is not God's freedom. The story of Scripture is God choosing a people so that through them he might save everyone who will trust in the promises (like the Isaac story) and admit weakness (like the Jacob story).⁵⁴

Third, by making God's purpose unconditional election rather than electing some to the historical task of reaching others, Piper has had to equate the word that did not fail (9:6b) and the word that stands (9:11) with unconditional election. The “word” that has succeeded is God's sovereign electing word throughout history. He says,

Therefore what has “not fallen” but has “remained” active and effectual is *God's purpose which has come to expression throughout redemptive history* in manifold communications which may be summed up as “the word of God.” Romans 9:6b-13 is written to support this assertion. The support consists therefore in showing what in fact *the purpose of God has always been in his communications with Israel*.⁵⁵

Piper identifies this *purpose which has come to expression throughout redemptive history* and which *has always been in his communication with Israel* in the following sentence, “If Paul can show that God's ultimate ‘purpose according to election’ never included the salvation of

⁵³ This universal promise was repeated to Abraham in 22:18, given to Isaac in 26:4, and to Jacob in 28:14.

⁵⁴ This would undercut the lineage and law-keeping arguments of Paul's interlocutors.

⁵⁵ Piper, 50.

every individual Israelite, then the situation described in Rom 9:1-5 would not so easily jeopardize God's reliability."⁵⁶ Thus, for Piper, God's word that has not failed in 9:6 is his word of sovereign election of some to salvation.

But I ask, "Is this the revealed purpose of God in the Old Testament narrative?" It is not, and Piper's assertion becomes biblically impossible because we have already noted that the Scripture Paul uses is "election to historical task" which Piper admits. Paul says that the words which God spoke in Old Testament times, these promises (9:4), have not failed. But none of these promises are unconditional election promises. They are all historical task promises. Thus, in 9:6, Paul cannot be talking about unconditional election.

Finally, the love/hate language of 9:13 has been shown to be covenant language used in antiquity to designate those who were in a covenant relationship and those who were not.⁵⁷ Paul quotes from Malachi who encouraged Israel to remain faithful to God. He would build up Israel and not Edom. I "love" Israel, i.e., I am in a covenant relationship with Israel. I "hate" Esau. I am not in a covenant relationship with the Edomites. But the entirety of Scriptural revelation is that God would one day save Edom. The apostle James quotes Amos' prophecy about Edom and uses it as a foundation for the Great Commission. Thus, the non-choice of Esau and God's "hatred" of Edom were only temporary measures until the coming of the Messiah who would rescue both Edomites and Ishmaelites.⁵⁸

⁵⁶ Ibid., 50.

⁵⁷ Moran, William L., "The Ancient Near Eastern Background of the Love of God in Deuteronomy," *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, 1963, 77-87. See also, Malina & Rohrbaugh, *Social Science Commentary on the Synoptic Gospels*, "Love/Hate," Fortress, Minneapolis, MN, 2003, 380.

⁵⁸ Isaiah 60:7 prophesies about the salvation of Ishmaelites (Kedar and Nebaioth). Amos 9:11 with Acts 15:16-17 uses an Edomite prophecy to speak of the salvation of the nations.

Engaging with Piper – The Sovereignty of God in Saying, “I will come.”

We come to the last portion of Piper’s exegesis of 9:6-13. I reserved this for last because understanding Piper’s point is dependent upon understanding his perspective on the election of Jacob over Esau where election is explicitly stated in 9:11-13. The election of Isaac over Ishmael, however, is not so clearly stated. If both illustrations in 9:6-13 support sovereign unconditional election, how does the Isaac/Ishmael story support it? Piper sees it this way.

[J]ust as Isaac was a child of promise in that God willed in advance for him to be the heir of the covenant promises and then worked sovereignly (“I will come!” 9:9) to fulfill his will, so also God wills in advance for particular individuals within Israel to be his “children” and then by his Spirit sovereignly begets them anew. Thus the *principle* of unconditional election, evident in God’s choice of Isaac to be heir of the covenant is applied now to Paul’s contemporaries to explain how it can be that only “some” (Rom 11:14) Israelites are saved....⁵⁹

This argument is easily answered. God did say that he would come. It was necessary for him to enliven Abraham’s and Sarah’s ability to conceive a child, but what Piper fails to acknowledge is the role of Abraham and Sarah’s faith to make this possible. Plus, Abraham and Sarah had to copulate for the conception to take place. God did not come and cause Sarah’s egg to conceive miraculously. He did come and enliven their bodies so that the natural way of conceiving children could occur. It was miraculous and synergistic. God worked and Abraham and Sarah had sexual relations. God promised and Abraham and Sarah believed.⁶⁰ This is why Isaac was chosen over Ishmael. Ishmael was born via God’s natural means of conceiving children with two people who had the ability to conceive. Isaac was born via God’s natural means of conceiving children with two people who did not have the ability to conceive. He was conceived because of faith in God’s promise. Because of that faith, God came, energized their

⁵⁹ Piper, 70.

⁶⁰ The New Testament emphasis is on faith. See Romans 4:19-22; Hebrews 11:11-12.

bodies, Isaac was conceived and born, and he was chosen to be the covenant-bearer as a paradigm that God's purposes for the world can only go forward by faith in the promises.⁶¹

Conclusion

Piper's effort in Romans 9 is inspirational. His love for God's word, submission to how he sees it, and attention to detail are laudable. But his exegesis fails. His attempt at coherence does not work. All passages are election to historical task. The dilemma of Israel's failure to be saved is not necessarily permanent and is not due to election but unbelief. He misses the paradigm of faith and humility in the stories of Isaac/Ishmael and Jacob/Esau because he can see only a paradigm of unconditional election. He has failed to see that God's choice of Jacob over Esau was about distinctives. He made the biblical narrative about election rather than God's plan to reach the world. He failed to see that God's coming to enliven Abraham and Sarah also required their faith, and he equated "God's word" in 9:6 with a word of unconditional election rather than his word of bringing salvation to the nations.

It is my hope that these pages will not produce strife, but a deeper look with reverence and humility at God's word, that we may understand his purpose and commit to advance his ministry of reconciliation to the world.

⁶¹ Piper, 68-69. Piper expounds upon the theme of a child of promise and emphasizes this is a term for salvation and not just historical task. Yet, what Piper fails to acknowledge is that the Isaac/Ishmael passages such as Galatians 3-4, never say anything about election. Their emphasis is on faith in the Messiah in contrast to the works of the Law. Isaac was chosen because his story was a story of faith. Ishmael's was not. The reason Jews lost their status is that they did not pursue God's covenant purpose by faith which is Paul's conclusion in 9:30-33.

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